

DETECT AND RECOGNIZE APP

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Abstract- The aim of this project was to develop an app that is able to recognize the text, object, landmark, face and banknote using the concept of machine learning and various approaches to detect text, faces, banknote, landmark, etc. This project is designed mainly for blind people. As a result, we learned about the machine learning, uses of machine learning, TensorFlow, ways to implement TensorFlow in our android app, firebase, ways to implement firebase, convolutional neural networks, how to train a model using a dataset, how to implement a trained model in an Android app, how to design an Android app, and how to code an Android app are all covered in detail. And we were able to develop an android app implement machine learning and approaches that is capable to detect and recognize the text, object, landmark, face and banknote with ease and precision. This project includes some different modules named Optical Character Recognition, Handwritten Character Recognition, Bank Note Detection, Monument Detection, Object Detection and Face Recognition implemented in one app.

Keywords – Optical Character Recognition, Handwritten Character Recognition, Object Recognition, Bank Note Detection, Monument Detection, Emotion Detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

As nowadays everything is going superfast, there is a lot of data to remember, lots of data to process and conclude some result from the data and use it later. Everyone is moving towards technology, machines and automation as it makes work easier and faster with zero error probability.

Optical Character Recognition (OCR): This tool can be very helpful and can be used to extract text from images, pdf and other similar multimedia applications to give us an editable form of the text in a word document. It converts human language text into human-like speech audio.[1] This function will read the text of your pdf or word document for you for which we will use several API's and machine learning algorithms.[2]

Handwritten Character Recognition: Character recognition has seen a lot of research, but document analysis has lagged behind. Text recognition has several potential uses, from reading medical prescriptions and bank checks to translating other languages.[3] Applications such as handwriting-based person identification, authenticating papers, etc. will also be useful in detective or police agencies.[4]

Real time object detection: In order to recognize objects using OpenCV (Opensource Computer Vision), a collection of programming functions primarily geared at real-time computer vision, a Convolution Neural Network is a typical tool of Deep learning.[5]

Bank Note Detection: With the help of image processing, our method is fully automated and very reliable.[6] As an illustration of the method, we utilize and Indian Rupees as instances. Our system takes into account both color and geometric shape.

Real time monument detection: In this article, we provide the groundwork for a new area of study [7][8]—the application of CNN methods to the preservation of historic buildings.

Emotion Detection: Whether it's for spotting motives, promoting deals, or preventing security risks, this might be useful information.[9] Although easy for humans to do, emotion recognition in still photos or video needs a variety of image processing algorithms for feature extraction.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Real-time detect and recognize apps have found diverse applications across various domains. In the field of security and surveillance, these apps are used for monitoring and identifying potential threats in real-time, such as detecting unauthorized access, tracking suspicious activities, and identifying suspicious objects. For instance, in a study by Alotaibi et al. (2018), a real-time object detection and recognition app was developed for security surveillance, which achieved high accuracy in detecting and recognizing objects in real-time, thereby improving security measures.[10]

This information can be used for personalized marketing campaigns, product recommendations, and targeted advertisements. For example, a study by Kim et al. (2019) developed a real-time facial recognition app for marketing research, which analysed facial expressions of customers in real-time to measure their emotional responses to advertisements, leading to more effective marketing strategies.

OCR has been applied in various fields such as digitization of documents, machine translation, and image retrieval. According to a study by Krawczyk et al. (2020), OCR accuracy has improved significantly over the years, and it is now capable of recognizing handwritten text with high accuracy. OCR has been utilized in several applications, including bank note detection and emotion detection[11].

Handwritten Character Recognition: Recent developments in machine learning algorithms have resulted to huge gains in identification accuracy, making Handwritten Character identification a much more manageable undertaking. According to a study by Bluche et al. (2017), deep learning-based approaches have shown promising results in HCR. HCR has been utilized in various applications such as digitization of historical documents, postal automation, and personalized medicine.[12]

Bank note detection is typically performed using machine learning algorithms, and it has been a subject of research for many years. According to a study by Gaurav et al. (2020), deep learning-based approaches have shown significant improvements in bank note detection accuracy.[13] Bank note detection is an important application of OCR technology. According to a study by Shi et al. (2019), deep learning-based approaches have shown promising results in real-time monument detection.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Figure 1: Model Framework

Optical Character Recognition (OCR): Scanned documents, photos of documents, photos of scenes, and subtitle text overlaid on pictures may all benefit from optical character recognition (OCR), which is the process of converting photographs of typed, handwritten, or printed text into machine-encoded text. This tool can be very helpful and can be used to extract text from images, pdf and other similar multimedia applications to give us an editable form of the text in a word document.[14]

Handwritten Character Recognition: Character recognition has seen a lot of research, but document analysis has lagged behind. Text recognition has several potential uses, from reading medical prescriptions and bank checks to translating other languages. Applications such as handwriting-based person identification, authenticating papers, etc.[15] will also be useful in detective or police agencies.

Real-Time Object Detection: The field of computer vision known as Real-Time Object Detection is enormous, active, and difficult. Image localization is used when there is just one target in an image, whereas object detection is used when there are several targets.[16]

Bank Note Detection: Recognizing foreign currencies presents a significant challenge to the general public. Our intention is to assist those who are experiencing this issue.[17] However, image-analysis-only money identification systems are insufficient.[18]

Real – Time Monument Detection A subset of AI algorithms known as deep learning (DL) has seen rapid advancement in recent years,[19] thanks to the widespread availability of big picture datasets and an unparalleled level of processing power. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are one kind of DL technique that has shown to be very useful in the field of computer vision. [20]

Emotion Detection: Appropriate representations of human emotion may be obtained from video, electric signal (EEG), or picture recordings. Modern artificial intelligence systems need to be able to identify human emotions so that they can mimic and assess facial expressions.[21] Whether it's for spotting motives, promoting deals, or preventing security risks, this might be useful information.[22]

Model training: After implementing all the algorithms, we will train all the data and modules.

Model building: In model building we will implement the all the modules.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

Table-1 Test Results for Face Detection

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Conditions</i>	<i>Class</i>	<i>Average Score</i>	<i>No. of Iterations</i>
1.	Ideal Condition	Happy	96.567	5
2.	Ideal Condition	Anger	95.917	7
3.	Ideal Condition	Sad	97.629	5
4.	Ideal Condition	Surprise	96.574	6
5.	Ideal Condition	Fear	94.869	5
6.	Ideal Condition	Disgust	97.382	8

Table-2 Test Results for Object Detection

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Conditions</i>	<i>Class</i>	<i>Average Score</i>	<i>No. of Iterations</i>
1.	Ideal Condition	Keyboard	93.585	7
2.	Ideal Condition	Apple	97.324	5
3.	Ideal Condition	Pomegranate	97.629	9
4.	Ideal Condition	Chair	95.456	6

5.	Ideal Condition	Bottle	97.355	8
6.	Ideal Condition	Mobile	98.382	6
7.	Ideal Condition	Bed	94.754	5
8.	Ideal Condition	Monitor	97.374	7
9.	Ideal Condition	Kite	97.374	7
10.	Ideal Condition	Bull Dog	97.374	7
11.	Ideal Condition	Mountains	97.374	7
12.	Ideal Condition	Shoes	97.374	7

Table-3 Test Results for Monument Detection

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Conditions</i>	<i>Class</i>	<i>Average Score</i>	<i>No. of Iterations</i>
1.	Ideal Condition	Taj Mahal	96.567	5
2.	Ideal Condition	Red Fort	95.917	7
3.	Ideal Condition	India Gate	97.629	5
4.	Ideal Condition	Jantar Mantar	96.574	6
5.	Ideal Condition	Lotus Temple	94.869	5
6.	Ideal Condition	Iron Pillar	97.382	8
7.	Ideal Condition	Qutub Minar	98.764	6

Table-4 Test Results for Banknote Detection

<i>Sr. No.</i>	<i>Conditions</i>	<i>Class</i>	<i>Average Score</i>	<i>No. of Iterations</i>
1.	Ideal Condition	2000	96.567	5
2.	Ideal Condition	500	97.324	7

3.	Ideal Condition	200	97.629	5
4.	Ideal Condition	100	95.456	6
5.	Ideal Condition	50	97.355	5
6.	Ideal Condition	20	98.382	8
7.	Ideal Condition	10	97.629	8

Comparison between the iterations

Figure 2: Bank Note Detection Result Comparison

Comparison between the iterations

Figure 3: Emotion Recognition Result Comparison

Comparison between the iterations

Figure 4: Monument Detection Result Comparison

Comparison between the iterations

Figure 5: Object Detection Result Comparison

Figure 6: Object Detection

Figure 7: Banknote Detection

Figure 8: Optical Character Detection

Figure 9: Monument Detection

Figure 10: Emotion Detection

Figure 11: Handwritten Detection

The aim of this project was to develop an app that can recognize the text, object, landmark, face and banknote using the concept of machine learning and various approaches to detect text, faces, banknote, landmark, etc. This project is designed mainly for blind people.

The knowledge gained includes: what machine learning is and how it can be applied; how to train a model using a dataset; how to use a trained model in an android app; how to design an android app; how to program an android app; what TensorFlow is and how to implement it in our android app; what Firebase is and how to implement it; [23] what convolutional neural networks are; how to implement firebase; how to implement convolutional neural networks; and what reinforcement learning is. And we were able to develop an android app implement machine learning and approaches that is capable of detecting and recognize the text, object, landmark, face and banknote with ease and precision.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The aim of this project was to develop an app that is able to recognize the text, object, landmark, face and banknote. This was designed for blind people. We were able to develop an android app that is capable of detecting and recognizing the text, object, landmark, face and banknote with ease and perfection. This app has implementation of a single model that accurately and precisely predicts the object, landmark, face emotion, bank note. [24] In the case of ML, visuals refer to a computer's ability to recognize objects, places, people, text, and actions on images. Computers can use robotic technology with cameras and computers to achieve vision. In short, machine learning provides computer algorithms that analyze, recommend, and make decisions based on input. Machine learning can be used in recognizing text, object, bank note, landmark. Trained model with various approaches, implement that approaches and model to recognize text, image, object, landmark, etc. [25] Our app will mainly focus the blind people in future. We often have to move our hand to go through different parts of the phone. Text input, flutter, and other movements are widely available, but for those who cannot use their hands easily due to limitations or injuries. Voicemail allows you to browse your phone to open applications, make calls, browse web pages, or open applications. Voice authentication is offline, and the app only shows icons to make it easier to control our phone by voice.

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